

Another Structure of Weakly Left C-wrpp Semigroups

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Abstract : It is known that a left C-wrpp semigroup can be described as curler structure of a left band and a C-wrpp semigroup. In this paper, we introduce the class of weakly left C-wrpp semigroups which includes the class of weakly left C-rpp semigroups as a subclass. We shall particularly show that the spined product of a left C-wrpp semigroup and a right normal band is a weakly left C-wrpp semigroup. Some equivalent characterizations of weakly left C-wrpp semigroups are obtained. Results obtained by Tang, Du-Shum and Zhang are extended and strengthened.

Keywords : Left C-wrpp semigroup, left quasi normal regular band, weakly left C-wrpp semigroup

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